

Disease intensity on flag leaves and panicles, unfilled grain percentage, and grain yield were measured. Flag leaf lesion counts and percentage of diseased grains/panicle were based on 50 randomly collected tillers/ plot.

Treatments differed significantly, but did not reduce flag leaf and grain infection much (see table). Grain infection was negatively correlated with percentage of unfilled grain ($r = -0.84^{**}$) and grain yield ($r = -0.84^{**}$),

but differences among the test fungicides were not significant. Blotter test determined that 75% of seeds collected from sprayed fields were associated with *H. oryzae*. That seed lot showed only 39% germination. □

Distribution and severity of rice seedling diseases in boro seedbeds in Bangladesh

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We surveyed rice seedbed diseases in some northwestern districts during the Nov-Mar boro season. Six diseases—bakanae (Bak), blast (Bl), brown spot (BS), damping-off (DO), root knot (RK), and seedling blight (Sb)—were found in 48 locations. Commonly grown rice were BR1, BR3, BR8, BR9, IR8, Pajam, Purbachi, and some local varieties.

DO was found everywhere, irrespective of variety (see table). RK was the second most common disease; it was not found in alkaline belts of Rajshahi district. Its intensity and severity were highest in sandy soil, especially near riverbanks, even in seedbeds with little standing water, irrespective of varieties sown.

BS was found in seedbeds that suffered from water stress. Bak affected seedlings of Purbachi, Khaily boro (local cultivar), and BR16. Bl was found mainly on Pajam and Iratom seedlings.

Distribution of seedling diseases as observed in boro seedbeds during January 1987 in northwestern districts of Bangladesh.

District	Disease frequency in survey area ^a						Total
	Bak	Bl	BS	DO	RK	Sb	
Bogra	6 (18.2)	0	6 (18.2)	12 (36.4)	9 (27.2)	0	33
Dinajpur	0	0	0	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	0	4
Gaibandha	2 (25.0)	0	2 (25.0)	2 (25.0)	2 (25.0)	0	8
Gazipur	0	2 (12.5)	1 (25.0)	2 (25.0)	2 (25.0)	1 (12.5)	8
Jalpur	1 (12.5)	0	1 (12.5)	3 (37.5)	3 (37.5)	0	8
Lalmonirhat	1 (33.3)	0	0	1 (33.3)	1 (33.3)	0	3
Mymensingh	2 (11.8)	3 (17.6)	3 (17.6)	6 (35.3)	3 (17.6)	0	17
Natore	1 (11.1)	0	3 (33.3)	3 (33.3)	2 (22.2)	0	9
Pabna	0	0	3 (37.5)	4 (50.0)	1 (12.5)	0	8
Rajshahi	0	0	2 (33.3)	2 (33.3)	1 (16.7)	1 (16.7)	6
Rangpur	2 (14.3)	1 (7.1)	1 (7.1)	5 (35.7)	5 (35.7)	0	14
Tangail	0	3 (16.7)	2 (11.1)	6 (33.3)	7 (38.9)	0	18
Total	15 (11.0)	9 (6.6)	24 (17.6)	48 (35.3)	38 (27.9)	2 (1.5)	136
DI	4 [3-5]	8 [7-9]	5 [3-7]	6 [3-9]	5 [3-7]	3 [1-5]	

^a Figures in parentheses show percentage of the disease in the district; those within brackets show disease index. DI 1 = lowest disease intensity, 9 = highest disease intensity.

Severity as high as disease index 8 was concentrated in Mymensingh, Tangail, Gazipur, and Rangpur districts. Sb was

found in only two locations. More than one disease was observed in the same seedbed in some locations. □

Managing rice sheath rot (ShR) disease in Kerala, India

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Field trials to evaluate crop nutrition schedules for managing rice ShR disease

have shown that sources of N and method of application can influence disease incidence and grain damage.

A field experiment during the first crop season (May-Sep 1985) at the Cropping Systems Research Centre, Karamana, used susceptible variety Jyothi to evaluate crop nutrition schedules for managing ShR.

The fertilizer level used was 70-35-52.5 kg NPK/ha, the recommended rate in disease endemic areas. Sources were

farmyard manure (FYM), urea, and ammonium sulfate for N; superphosphate for P; and muriate of potash for K. Except for FYM, all forms of N were applied in three splits, half as basal and half in two equal topdressings. K was applied in two equal splits, basal and as topdressing. All P was applied as basal.

Carboxin (0.1% spray), widely recommended for ShR control, was sprayed with two fertilizer treatments